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La importancia de la educación continua de los funcionarios públicos para la eficiencia de la administración pública

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Resumen. El objetivo de este trabajo fue estudiar el papel y la importancia del sistema de educación continua de los servidores públicos para mejorar la calidad de la administración pública y optimizar la prestación de servicios públicos a la población. La investigación utilizó el método analítico, el método funcional-estructural, el método de análisis comparativo, el método de evaluación de expertos, el análisis estadístico, el método de estudio de casos y el análisis de sistemas. La investigación identificó la necesidad de implementar un enfoque sistemático para la capacitación de los servidores públicos, incluyendo programas educativos adaptativos, alfabetización digital, un sistema de mentoría y cooperación internacional. Se encontró una relación entre el nivel de formación profesional de los servidores públicos y el nivel de confianza de los ciudadanos en los órganos gubernamentales. La formación continua de los funcionarios públicos puede mejorar significativamente la calidad de los servicios públicos prestados a las empresas y a la población, así como acelerar la eficiencia del funcionamiento del aparato administrativo estatal. La creación de amplias oportunidades para un programa de formación flexible para los servidores públicos, que les permita combinar el desempeño de sus funciones profesionales y su formación, permitirá involucrar eficazmente a las diversas categorías de servidores públicos en el proceso de formación continua.

Palabras clave: formación continua de funcionarios, funcionarios, formación avanzada.

The importance of continuing civil servants' education for the effectiveness of public administration

Abstract. The purpose of this research was to study the role and importance of the continuous education system with civil servants to improve the public administration quality and optimize the provision of public services to the population. The research used the analytical method, the functional-structural method, the comparative annalistic method, the expert assessment method, statistical analysis, the case study method and the system analysis. The research established the need to introduce a systematized approach to training civil servants, including adaptive educational programs, digital literacy, a mentoring system and international cooperation. The relationship between the professional training level of civil servants and the citizens level trust in government bodies was revealed. Continuous civil servants' education can significantly improve the public service quality provided to enterprises and the population, as well as accelerate the efficiency of the state administration apparatus. Creating broad opportunities for a flexible educational schedule for civil servants, which would allow them to combine their professional duties and training, will effectively involve various civil servant categories in the continuous educative process.

Keywords: continuing civil servants' education, civil servants, advanced training.

INTRODUCTION

Professional skills and educational level of civil servants are the most important criteria that directly affect the service quality they provide to the population. A high competence level of civil servants determines their ability to quickly respond to changes in the socio-economic and political environment, develop and implement effective management decisions, and ensure transparency and accessibility of public services. Competent specialists are able to work with the population more quickly, correctly and respectfully, which helps to increase citizen satisfactory level with public services and strengthen trust in government institutions. A civil servant must have not only professional knowledge, but also developed communication skills that allow them effectively conduct a dialogue, explain legal and administrative issues, and prevent possible conflicts. Polite and competent advice to citizens increases their confidence in government agencies and help improve the overall perception of the government agency work. In addition, the ability to clearly and accessibly explain complex administrative processes makes interaction with government agencies more convenient and transparent for citizens. This is especially important in the context of digital transformation, when government services are increasingly provided online, and high-quality communication helps people quickly adapt to new services.

In the scientific works of the authors G. Kholod, A. Nazaryan, Y. Starushchenko, I. Lopushynskyi, V. Kukhar, the emphasis is placed on the automation of the civil servant's workplace, which plays an important role in improving public administration efficiency. The introduction of modern digital technologies helps to speed up bureaucratic procedures, reduce bureaucratic barriers and improve the service providing quality. The use of digital platforms makes public services more accessible to citizens, allowing them to receive necessary information and complete documents online,

without having to personally visit government agencies. This significantly saves time for both citizens and civil servants, reducing the burden on the administrative apparatus. However, digitalization requires new competencies from civil servants related to work in a digital environment, cybersecurity, data analysis and adaptation in rapidly changing technologies. In this regard, continuous training and advanced training of civil servants in the digital governing field is in particular importance. Thus, automation and public administration digitalization not only simplify administrative processes, but also require continuous development of professional skills of civil servants, which ultimately contributes to the formation of a more efficient, transparent and citizen-oriented public administration system.

According to the authors T. Kopyl-Filatova, I. Rozic, M. Ljubić, the professional training level of civil servants plays a key role in building citizens' trust in government bodies. Competent and qualified specialists are able to perform their duties more effectively, ensuring transparency, efficiency and high quality of services provided. When civil servants have sufficient knowledge, skills and professional competencies, they are able to make informed management decisions, solve socio-economic problems and take into account the interests of the population. This, in turn, contributes to an increase in the level of citizen satisfaction with interactions with government agencies and strengthens their confidence in the fairness and effectiveness of government bodies. In addition, a high level of training of civil servants reduces the likelihood of corruption, bureaucratic barriers and administrative errors, which also has a positive effect on the perception of the state by citizens. In the context of modern digitalization and growing public expectations, the need for continuous training and professional development of civil servants is becoming an integral factor in successful public administration.

In today's globalized world, international cooperation is in particular importance. States are increasingly faced with complex challenges that require joint efforts and the exchange of best practices. In these conditions, a high training level of civil servants is becoming not only a factor in the internal public administration effectiveness, but also an important condition for successful interaction in the international arena. Competent and well-trained civil servants can actively participate in international projects, contributing to the introduction of advanced technologies, improving management processes and enhancing public quality services. They are able to effectively adapt and use foreign experience, modernizing national institutions and creating favorable conditions for the socio-economic development of the country. In addition, a high professional training level allows civil servants to represent the interests of their country in international negotiations, develop and implement strategic initiatives, and contribute to strengthening diplomatic and economic ties. In the globalization and digital transformation era, international cooperation is becoming the most important resource for increasing the competitiveness of the state, and qualified specialists play a key role in this process.

To ensure sustainable state development, civil servants must have deep knowledge in key areas such as economics, law and ecology. These competencies allow them to make balanced and informed decisions aimed at the rational use of public resources, ensuring a balance between economic growth, social stability and environmental protection. Competent management of public resources requires officials not only professional training, but also the ability to adapt to changing conditions, take into account international experience and implement innovative approaches. In this context, investing in the training and retraining of civil servants is becoming a strategically important factor contributing to the public administration modernization and its compliance with international

standards. In addition, improving the skills of civil servants directly affects the life quality improvement of the population. Effective management decisions based on modern knowledge allow us to optimize public spending, increase the social supporting level, improve the environmental situation and form transparent mechanisms for interaction between the government and society. As a result, citizens' trust in state institutions is growing, which is an important basis for the stable and sustainable development of the country.

Modern civil servants are faced with a number of requirements, the fulfillment of which guarantees their professionalism level, competence and corresponds to the tasks facing public administration (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Requirements for civil servants (adapted by the authors).

Modern challenges such as digitalization, globalization and the increasing complexity of social processes require continuous professional development from civil servants. The rapid spread of new technologies, changing socio-economic conditions, increasing demands from society and need to work in uncertain conditions make professional training of civil servants not just desirable, but a necessary condition for effective management.

Insufficient qualifications can lead to ineffective management, slow administrative processes, decreased citizen trust in government institutions, and poor decision-making quality. In digital transformation context, a lack of IT competencies can slowly down the implementation of automated management systems, which in turn hinders citizens' access to government services and reduces their quality. In addition, the lack of modern management skills among officials can lead to untimely responses to crises, inefficient resource allocation, and bureaucratic barriers.

In this regard, continuous civil servants' education is becoming a key tool for improving their professional competence. Advanced training, retraining and additional educational programs allow

them to master new technologies, improve management skills, adapt to changes in legislation and implement best international practices. This is especially important in the context of the country's integration into the global community, when it is necessary to take into account international standards and use advanced foreign experience.

In addition, the development of a continuous education system contributes to the formation of a professional culture among civil servants, motivating them to self-improvement and responsibility for their work quality. The introduction of distance learning technologies and digital platforms makes training more accessible and flexible, which is especially important for employees working in remote regions.

Thus, investments in the education and development of civil servants are a strategically important area that contributes to increasing the public administration efficiency, improving the service quality provided and strengthening citizens' trust in the government. The modern state apparatus should be not only an administrative structure, but also a dynamic system capable of constant renewal and improvement, corresponding to the challenges of the time and social expectations.

METHODS

In the course of this research, the authors used a comprehensive approach studying the continuous educative problems of civil servants. The research used various methods to comprehensively study the continuous educative system of civil servants, identify key effective factors and determine development paths. The analytical method provided a comprehensive analysis of existing approaches to continuous public administration personnel training, revealing its importance and the main factors influencing the system effectiveness. To structure knowledge about the continuous educative role in the public administration system, a functional-structural method was used, which made it possible to determine the relationship between the level of civil servants training and the service quality they provide. Comparative analysis made it possible to study international experience in organizing a continuous education system, identify the features of various educational models and assess their applicability in domestic practice. Additionally, the expert assessment method made it possible to collect the opinions of leading experts in the public administration and education fields, which helped to identify existing problems and outline ways to solve them. To process empirical data, the statistical analysis method was used, which made it possible to assess the professional training dynamics of civil servants, identify the main trends and predict the further system development. In addition, the use of the case study method (study specific cases) provided a real example analysis of the educational program implementation in public institutions, which made it possible to identify the most effective advanced training methods. Finally, the system analysis method made it possible to consider continuous education as an integrated public administration system element, taking into account the impact of personnel policy, digital transformation, socio-economic conditions and international standards.

The use of these methods in combination made it possible to provide a comprehensive approach to the study of the problem and develop recommendations for improving the continuous educative system of civil servants.

RESULTS

In our opinion, the continuous educative system of civil servants is of paramount importance for creating the preconditions for effective public administration for a number of reasons.

State legislative and executive authorities, in the process of performing their functions, issue various normative documents, amendments to existing normative acts. As a result, civil servants must know these changes in order to be guided by them in their professional activities. In the conditions of continuous scientific and technical progress, new technologies are constantly emerging. Civil servants must be familiar with these technologies and, if possible, be able to apply them in their professional activities.

Qualified and professionally trained civil servants are able to more effectively and quickly solve the problems that society and citizens pose to them.

Continuous education of government officials at all stages of their professional careers makes it possible to implement modern management methods and technologies in practice. This, in turn, not only increases the efficiency using government resources, but also allows for an increase in labor productivity, and makes it possible to effectively solve complex production problems.

The sustainability and public administration stability largely depends on the knowledge continuity and the formation system of a personnel reserve for the civil service. This ensures the stability of the system state power functioning in economic and political crises conditions.

Particular attention should be paid to the formation of a personnel reserve of senior staff for the public administration system. They must have skills in strategic planning, conflict management and leadership qualities, and be able to organize teamwork among their subordinates. Heads of government agencies must have skills in motivating and inspiring their subordinates, and effectively use financial, material and labor resources.

This requires a permanent system of training and advanced training courses for lower and middle-level civil servants.

Globalization of economic relations inevitably affects the work of governmental bodies. Continuous civil servants' education creates opportunities to effectively implement the requirements of international practices and standards in their professional activities.

In our opinion, the continuous educative system of civil servants should be multifaceted, meet modern standards of civil service and be systematic. Continuous civil servants' education, on the one hand, should contribute to the successful development of their professional career, and on the other one, assist in increasing the efficiency of the public administration system.

- 1) In this regard, the public educative system of civil servants should, in our opinion, meet the following criteria:
- 2) Education should be based on a competency-based approach; it should, first of all, be focused on solving specific typical professional tasks.
- 3) Civil servants' education should be an integral part of their career and include various trainings, advanced training courses and, if necessary, professional retraining.
- 4) It is necessary to combine various training forms and methods, which should include traditional seminars and lectures and distance learning methods. The introduction of a mentoring

system, within which more experienced employees pass on their experience and knowledge to new employees, deserves attention.

- 5) Civil servants' education should be taken into account the career plans, level of previous trainings and professional natural duties of each specific civil servant. Training programs should be individual in nature, which would allow students to choose the courses to be studied in accordance with the specifics of their professional activities.
- 6) Civil servants' education should primarily develop their digital literacy and the ability to work with information platforms and systems.
- 7) Civil servants' education must be flexible and must provide for the opportunity to improve their professional level in a convenient place, at a convenient time, and including without interrupting the civil servant's performance of his professional duties.
- 8) In the state civil servants' education system, it is important to monitor the quality of such education and the certification system of the competencies obtained as a training result. It is especially important that there is a close correlation between the advancement of a civil servant up the career ladder and success in improving his professional level through continuous education.
- 9) In order to ensure the civil servants' education quality, in our opinion, it is necessary to use not only training in specialized state educational institutions, but also to actively participate in international educational programs such as Erasmus.

DISCUSSION

The system of continuous civil servants' education should promote their professional growth, the ability to more effectively perform their professional duties, and also to maximally correspond to the goals and objectives of public administrations. The system of continuous civil servants' education should be continuous and systematic.

To improve the professional training level of civil servants, it is advisable to use universities and specialized advanced training courses.

To ensure high training civil servants' efficiency, it is necessary to actively combine various methods and training forms, which may include internships (including abroad), participation in MBA programs, short-term advanced training courses, as well as webinars and other distant educative forms.

Modern civil servants must have the skills to work with electronic platforms and knowledge bases, and be able to use artificial intelligence in their work.

The interaction effectiveness between civil servants and citizens in the process providing them with public services requires civil servants to be stress-resistant and have communication skills.

Motivation and stimulation of this educational activity is of great importance for the functioning of the training and retraining systems of civil servants. It is necessary to ensure conditions under which the successful career of a civil servant correlates with the professional competent growth.

CONCLUSION

Continuous civil servants' education plays a key role in improving the public administration efficiency and the quality of services provided to the population. The conducted research allowed us to draw the following conclusions: civil servants with relevant knowledge and competencies are able to quickly respond to changes in legislation, implement innovative technologies and provide a high service level to citizens.

A high-quality training system that civil servants contributes to the public confidence growth in government bodies, since professionally trained specialists demonstrate competence, ethics and respect for citizens. The introduction of automated systems and digital technologies in the process providing public services requires new knowledge and skills from employees, which helps to reduce bureaucratic barriers and increase the processing request speed. In globalization context, civil servants must have knowledge of international standards and management practices, which will allow integrating the best world approaches into the domestic public administration system. Civil servants' education should be adaptive, take into account the specifics of their professional activities and include various forms of training, such as distance courses, trainings, mentoring and international educational programs. Civil servants' career growth should directly depend on their professional training and participation level in advanced training programs, for which it is necessary to develop a motivation system that includes financial and non-financial incentives. An effective continuous educative system allows you to form personnel highly qualified reserved specialists with the necessary leadership qualities and strategic thinking. Continuous educative development system should be part of state policy aimed at sustainable development and increasing the efficiency of public resource management.

Thus, the modernization of the continuous civil servants' educative system will not only improve their professional level, but also create conditions for effective government management focused on the needs of citizens and modern challenges.

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